

FAMILY EDUCATION IS AN ETERNAL SOCIAL-PHILOSOPHICAL PROBLEM

Gafurov Doniyor Oripovich

Bukhara Institute of Engineering and Technology is an associate professor of the "Social Sciences" department, doctor of philosophy (PhD).

Annotatsiya: In this article, Eastern thinkers emphasized the role of family and family education in personal education and development. It is stated that they expressed valuable thoughts about a number of qualities such as honesty, purity, bravery, eloquence, kindness, truthfulness, etc., which can be developed only in the family, in their philosophical-ethical, sociological and psychological views.

Key words: Family, education, science, upbringing, sustainable development, spiritual maturity.

СЕМЕЙНОЕ ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ – ВЕЧНАЯ СОЦИАЛЬНО-ФИЛОСОФСКАЯ ПРОБЛЕМА

Гафуров Дониёр Орипович

Бухарский инженерно-технологический институт – доцент кафедры «Общественные науки», доктор философских наук (PhD).

Аннотация: В этой статье восточные мыслители подчеркнули роль семьи и семейного воспитания в воспитании и развитии личности. Констатируется, что они высказали ценные мысли о ряде качеств, таких как честность, чистота, храбрость, красноречие, доброта, правдивость и др., которые можно развивать только в семье, в их философско-этических, социологических и психологических воззрениях.

Ключевые слова: Семья, образование, наука, воспитание, устойчивое развитие, духовная зрелость.

OILA TARBIYASI – AZALIY IJTIMOIIY-FALSAFIY MUAMMO SIFATIDA

G‘afurov Doniyor Oripovich

Buxoro muhandislik-texnologiya instituti “Ijtimoiy fanlar” kafedrasida dotsenti, falsafa fanlari doktori (PhD).

Annotatsiya: *Ushbu maqolada Sharq mutaffakirlari shaxs tarbiyasi va kamolotida oilaning, oilaviy tarbiyaning rolini yuqori qo'yishgan. Ular faqat oiladagina rivojlanishi mumkin bo'lgan sifatlari - halollik, poklik, mardliq, so'zomollik, mehribonlik, xaqgo'ylik kabi qator fazilatlariga oid qimmatli fikrlarni o'z falsafiy-etik, sotsiologik va psixologik qarashlarida ifodalab berganligi bayon qilingan.*

Tayanch so'zlar: *Oila, ta'lim, fan, tarbiya, barqaror taraqqiyot, ma'naviy yetuklik.*

In our country, the family is considered as the basis of society, an important link, it is not only a personal issue, but it is also of social importance. After all, a perfect person is brought up and grows up in an all-around prosperous, fluffy, healthy family. It is not for nothing that raising a healthy generation and creating a healthy family environment is recognized as a priority issue of state policy. As a socio-philosophical problem, as the human society progresses, it is observed that family relationships, which are the most intimate and closest among interpersonal relationships, improve and become complicated in their own way.

The President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoev said: "the task of strengthening a healthy environment in our families, neighborhoods, and our entire society, educating young people, preserving our peaceful life, and the purity of our holy religion is gaining great importance today", emphasized the need to be responsible for family stability and youth education. The issues of family upbringing, which is one of the main problems of social life, have been the focus of attention of the most advanced people of religious and worldly science, great scientists and sages for centuries. The great ideas of Abu Nasr Farabi, Abu Rayhan Beruni, Abu Ali Ibn Sina, Yusuf Khos Khajib, Kaikovus, Alisher Navai, Rezauddin Ibn Fakhridin and others, who are considered the great scholars of the East, are of great social and ideological importance for modern science.

Eastern thinkers have emphasized the role of family and family education in personal education and development. In their philosophical-ethical, sociological and psychological views, they expressed valuable thoughts about a number of qualities that can be developed only in the family - honesty, purity, bravery, eloquence, kindness, truthfulness.

It is known that the Qur'an and Hadiths, which are the holy sources of Islam, give a lot of space to issues of manners, roles and responsibilities of women in marriage, relations between husband and wife, raising children, running a family, marriage and love: "Along with honoring your children, ethics - Improve your manners"; "No father

can give his child a greater legacy than good manners". Abu Nasr Farabi's general philosophical views on human perfection, happiness, morals, education, attitude to religion, based on folk traditions, enriched the theory of ethics. According to his teachings, family members' sincere relations and affection towards each other constitute the happiness of people in the family. Also, the conclusions that each parent is the primary teacher and guide for their children show how important it is even today.

Encyclopedist-scientist Abu Rayhan Beruni said, "A person is obliged to unite with his relatives in society, the purpose of which is to support each other and to do work for each person to provide for himself and others".

A.R.Beruniy considers his health and mental purity as the basis for family members, spouses to ensure family harmony. A person's morals are a great contribution to family ethics by his thoughts that he should be an example of behavior, behavior culture, life, and family stability.

Allama Abu Ali Ibn Sina, whose encyclopedic knowledge was recognized in the system of family relations, had pedagogical and psychological views built on a social basis. He advised parents that it is better to educate a child by personal example than by inflicting severe corporal punishment on him. Alloma emphasized the role of the family in matters of moral education. In his work "Tadbiri Manzil" "The head of the family should master the issues of family upbringing both theoretically and practically. If the head of the family is inexperienced, he does not conduct education well, ultimately he cannot achieve positive results, bad education can have a bad effect not only on this family, but also on the neighbors and neighborhood. "Child education in the family is the primary duty of parents, regardless of their position in society", he believes.

In short, "Parents should influence the child's spirit not only with words, but also with actions".

His thoughts about the social and economic maturity necessary for starting a family are noteworthy: "If a young man learns a trade, can apply it in life, and can provide for the family thanks to his independent trade, his father should marry him".

The socio-philosophical views of the great thinker and poet of the 11th century, Yusuf Khos Khajib, are described in the book "Kutadgu Bilig" - "Knowledge that leads to happiness".

In his opinion, having and raising a child is a great happiness for every person. But this task imposes a great responsibility on the parents, it is both a duty and a debt for every parent to be able to cope with it. Yusuf Khos Khajib considered family upbringing as the basis of moral development of a child: "If a child's behavior is bad, it is not the child's fault, it is all the father's fault".

Kaikovus Unsurulmaoni - at the age of 63, he wrote "NIGHTMARE" for his son, in which he described his issues of child upbringing, family life, and personal development. The main idea in the book is to properly conduct education in the family. In his opinion: "If every child is intelligent and wise, parents should not refuse to show their love." He believes that it will be appropriate if education is carried out on the basis of the proverb "What you sow, you will reap" in this matter.

Enlightener Abdulla Avloni's work "Turkish Gulistan or Morality" is notable for its great contribution to family pedagogy and psychology.

In his socio-philosophical, psychological, educational views, the influence of the social environment, family conditions and people around the child is shown:

"Who does education? Where is it done? the question arises. To this question, "the first home education - This is a mother's task. If we answer that education of the second school and madrasah is the duty of the father, teacher, teacher and the government. Therefore, in the opinion of Abdulla Avloni, he recognized that the perfect education of a child depends not only on the family, but also on schools and public organizations, and interpreted the issue of education at the level of universal tasks.

The opinions expressed by Eastern thinkers from a philosophical and psychological point of view on the issue of family education, which is a kind of socio-philosophical problem, can be the most important lesson for generations in social life. The importance of this lesson is that it is implemented in the family as a centuries-old strong spiritual support through grandfather's education, father's example, mother's love, and serves to ensure the stability of families. After all, as President Shavkat Mirziyoyev said, "Our people should know that the family is sacred for us. If we don't save the family, we will lose our identity!"

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